

Biosystems and Ghosts

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Abstract: This paper presents the truths about separate life (soul), which can become a ghost after death, in living bodies (including human bodies) that are called biosystems.

Keywords: separate life, living body, soul

1. Introduction

We know that all living biosystems are comprised of some chemical elements [1]. In a discussion, the author of this article informed his colleague that no ghost comes from a person who dies, but he replied there are ghosts. Now, the author's question is: what are the chemical elements comprised of a ghost body.

2. Life Cycle of Biosystems

The chemical equation for the life of plant body is shown below:

The chemical equation for the life of animal body is given below:

Animal cells and plant cells are almost similar. The difference is that plants which produce oxygen are living by carbon dioxide, and animals are living by oxygen. Animal bodies including human bodies are living between their birth and death by respiration, nutrition, blood circulation, and cell growth [1].

3. Conclusion

In this article, we conclude that there is no separate life (soul), which can become a ghost after death, in living bodies (including human bodies).

References

[1] Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Composition_of_the_human_body.